

The Impact of Teacher Performance Management on the "Merdeka Mengajar" Platform on the Teaching and Learning Process

Ade Khairiyah¹, Rambat Nur Sasongko², Asti Putri Kartiwi³

¹Teacher in SMA Negeri 5 Bengkulu City and Graduate Student in the Master of Educational Administration Program, Faculty of Education, Universitas Bengkulu, Indonesia

^{2,3}Lecturers in the Master of Educational Administration Program, Faculty of Education, Universitas Bengkulu, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: This study aims to describe the impact of teacher performance management on the "Merdeka Mengajar" platform on the teaching and learning process at SMA Negeri 5 Bengkulu, Indonesia. This research employed a qualitative descriptive method, with data collected through interviews, observations, and document analysis. Data were analyzed inductively using the Miles and Huberman model. The findings indicate that performance planning helps guide teachers in selecting performance practices. Performance implementation serves as a tool for facilitating the teaching and learning process and professional development. Performance evaluation provides feedback to teachers on their teaching practices. Supporting factors include the availability of features on the "Merdeka Mengajar" platform, school support, professional development opportunities, and teachers' awareness and commitment. Inhibiting factors include limited time and workload, lack of supervision, unsynchronized platform features, implementation difficulties, and the absence of personal motivation and commitment among teachers.

KEYWORDS: "Merdeka Mengajar" Platform, Teacher Performance Management, Teaching and Learning Process

INTRODUCTION

Teachers hold a crucial position in education and are at the forefront of the educational process. To become a teacher requires high-level skills, dedication, and commitment, making the role of a teacher highly complex (Tirtoni, 2024). The duties and responsibilities of teachers must align with national educational standards and are evaluated through teacher performance.

The legal basis for teacher performance management in Indonesia is regulated by several government policies: Presidential Regulation of the Republic of Indonesia No. 95 of 2018 concerning the Electronic-Based Government System; Regulation of the Minister for Administrative and Bureaucratic Reform (PermenPANRB) No. 6 of 2022 on Performance Management of Civil Servants; PermenPANRB No. 1 of 2023 on Functional Positions; and the Regulation of the Director General of Teachers and Education Personnel (GTK) No. 7607/B.B1/HK.03/2023 of 2023 on Technical Guidelines for Teacher and Principal Performance Management (Imelda, 2024).

Nationally, teacher and principal performance management is carried out electronically via the *Platform Merdeka Mengajar* (PMM), which integrates an e-Performance feature linked to the National Civil Service Agency (BKN). The implementation of performance management on the PMM platform began in January 2024 (Imelda, 2024).

The *Platform Merdeka Mengajar* (PMM) is a recent innovation from the Ministry of Education, Culture, Research, and Technology of Indonesia, developed to support the implementation of the *Merdeka Curriculum*. It aims to help teachers access references, inspiration, and deeper understanding of the curriculum (Anggraini, 2024:1551). With the implementation of performance management through PMM, teachers' workloads are not expected to increase. In fact, it simplifies performance improvement by allowing teachers and school leaders to focus on a single performance indicator, based on their school's *Education Report Card* (Paudpedia, 2024).

Since early January 2024, the researcher's observations at SMA Negeri 5 Bengkulu revealed that teachers involved in the *Merdeka Mengajar* Platform (PMM) must plan their performance achievements with a minimum of 32 points and a maximum of 128 points per semester (Kemendikbudristek, 2023). However, most of the evidence submitted was derived from activities outside the classroom, such as sharing best practices, attending seminars/webinars, and uploading certificates or other documentation onto the PMM platform. This raises a critical question: Why does the majority of performance management evidence originate from activities outside the classroom?

An article published in *Media Literasi Nusantara (Melintas)* on January 24, 2024, titled “Is It True That Many Teachers Are Worried About Performance Management Being Implemented Through the Merdeka Mengajar Platform? Let’s Hear What the Character Education Expert Says!”, raised similar concerns. *Kompas Daily*, on January 30, 2024, published another article titled “Teachers Overwhelmed by Various Educational Applications.” On the same day, another *Melintas* article appeared titled “The Merdeka Curriculum Takes Its Toll: Teachers Busy with Administration and Training While Students Are Neglected.”

These observations and articles reflect the emergence of negative opinions regarding teacher performance management through the PMM. Teachers are becoming increasingly burdened with administrative tasks at the expense of their core responsibility as educators. Ideally, teachers should focus more on classroom teaching and student interaction, which are essential for promoting character education in schools (Shokhyatun, 2023).

Several previous studies have examined the impact of teacher performance on the quality of instruction. First, Pepito (2024), in his study titled “*Impact of Multitasking on Teachers’ Performance in Public Elementary Schools*,” found that multitasking negatively affects teaching quality. Teachers who must divide their attention between administrative duties and teaching are less likely to deliver optimal learning experiences for students, potentially resulting in poor academic outcomes and a need for additional interventions to enhance educational quality.

The second study, by An’ars (2022), examined the use of applications to measure teacher performance prior to the PMM. In his journal article titled “*Key Performance Indicator (KPI)-Based Information Systems in Measuring Teacher Performance*,” he explained the development of a performance evaluation system using KPI methods. The system included features for managing teacher data, assessing KPIs, and generating performance reports to determine whether a teacher’s performance was satisfactory. This automated system provided instant feedback on individual teacher performance.

The third study, by Munawir (2023), in a journal titled “*Understanding Teacher Performance Assessment (PKG)*,” emphasized the need for performance evaluations that contribute to the development of teacher performance profiles. These profiles serve as a foundation for future professional development plans. The study also recommended further research into the stages of performance evaluation, how to develop appropriate instruments, and how to analyze performance assessment results using empirical data.

Currently, instruments for evaluating teacher performance are integrated within the *Merdeka Mengajar* Platform (PMM), which requires teachers to follow all performance management procedures embedded within the system. However, this shift has affected the teaching and learning process in the classroom—raising important research questions. The rationale for this thesis research is based on several key considerations: (1) the topic has not been extensively studied; (2) the performance management process on the PMM is still ongoing and evolving; and (3) there is a need for scientific insight into the effects of teacher performance management on the teaching and learning process.

Based on the problem background, this study is entitled: “The Impact of Teacher Performance Management on the *Merdeka Mengajar* Platform (PMM) on the Teaching and Learning Process at SMA Negeri 5 Bengkulu.” The general research question is: What is the impact of teacher performance management on the *Merdeka Mengajar* Platform (PMM) on the teaching and learning process at SMA Negeri 5 Bengkulu?

This general question is further elaborated into the following specific research questions: (1) What is the impact of teacher performance planning on the *Merdeka Mengajar* Platform (PMM) on the teaching and learning process at SMA Negeri 5 Bengkulu?, (2) What is the impact of teacher performance implementation on the PMM on the teaching and learning process at SMA Negeri 5 Bengkulu?, (3) What is the impact of teacher performance evaluation on the PMM on the teaching and learning process at SMA Negeri 5 Bengkulu?, and (4) What are the supporting and inhibiting factors in managing teacher performance on the PMM that affect the teaching and learning process at SMA Negeri 5 Bengkulu?

The general objective of this study is to describe the impact of teacher performance management on the PMM platform on the teaching and learning process at SMA Negeri 5 Bengkulu. The specific objectives of this research are: (1) to describe the impact of performance planning on the PMM platform on the teaching and learning process at SMA Negeri 5 Bengkulu, (2) to describe the impact of performance implementation on the PMM platform on the teaching and learning process at SMA Negeri 5 Bengkulu, (3) to describe the impact of performance evaluation on the PMM platform on the teaching and learning process at SMA Negeri 5 Bengkulu, (4) to identify the supporting and inhibiting factors in managing teacher performance on the PMM platform that affect the teaching and learning process at SMA Negeri 5 Bengkulu.

METHOD

This study employed a qualitative descriptive research method. Qualitative descriptive research focuses on current problems and conducts analysis to obtain accurate data and information (Kurnia, 2023:86). It involves a deep understanding of the phenomena under investigation by collecting diverse and detailed data. Qualitative research is designed to explore social phenomena from the participants' perspectives, uncover natural conditions, and interpret their underlying meanings (Haryono, 2023:10).

By using a phenomenological approach, the researcher aimed to describe the condition of the research subjects based on observable and factual data. Therefore, this study intends to describe data obtained from the field—both written and oral—from the research subjects regarding the impact of teacher performance management on the *Merdeka Mengajar* Platform (PMM) on the teaching and learning process.

The research subjects consisted of teachers, serving as the main informants, who are under the Ministry of Education, Culture, Research, and Technology (Kemendikbudristek) and are actively engaged in the implementation of teacher performance management on the PMM platform. The study involved teachers from diverse backgrounds in terms of teaching experience, educational qualifications, and subject specializations.

The data collection techniques used in this research were interviews, observations, and documentation: (1) Interviews were conducted through direct interaction between the researcher and participants to gain a deep understanding of their experiences, perspectives, and views related to the studied phenomenon (Ardiansyah, 2023:4). In this study, in-depth interviews were conducted with teachers, principals, and students to gather insights into their experiences with teacher performance management on the PMM platform. (2) Observation is a technique that involves direct monitoring of participants and the context in which the phenomenon occurs, either in natural or research-designed settings. Observation allows the researcher to examine social interactions, behaviors, and relevant contextual factors (Ardiansyah, 2023:4). The researcher conducted direct observations in the school setting to understand how teachers use the PMM platform in their daily performance management. Observations included teacher-student interactions, technology use, and time management practices. (3) Documentation involves collecting data from documents, archives, or other written materials related to the phenomenon. These may include records, reports, correspondence, books, or official documents. Document analysis provides insights into historical contexts, policies, events, and developments relevant to the phenomenon (Ardiansyah, 2023:4). The researcher collected and analyzed related documents, such as lesson plans, performance reports, and administrative records, to assess teachers' workloads and how their performance management is reflected through the PMM platform.

The data analysis technique used in this study followed the Miles and Huberman model. This model involves an interactive and continuous process that continues until the data becomes saturated. The process includes three main stages: data reduction, data display, and conclusion drawing/verification (Kumala, 2022:254). Data Reduction is the process of selecting, focusing, simplifying, abstracting, and transforming raw data obtained from various sources such as field notes and interviews. It occurs throughout the research process, allowing the researcher to filter relevant data and summarize it in a meaningful way to identify emerging patterns. Data Display involves organizing and presenting the reduced data systematically, usually in the form of tables, graphs, matrices, or narratives. The goal is to make the data more understandable and to facilitate further analysis and conclusion drawing. Conclusion Drawing and Verification is the final step, where the researcher interprets the data by identifying patterns, themes, consistencies, and relationships. Preliminary conclusions are validated through rechecking, triangulation, or additional data confirmation to ensure credibility and reliability.

RESEARCH FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

This study aimed to describe the impact of teacher performance management on the *Merdeka Mengajar* Platform (PMM) on the teaching and learning process at SMA Negeri 5 Bengkulu. The specific objectives were to: describe the impact of teacher performance planning on the teaching and learning process, describe the impact of performance implementation, describe the impact of performance evaluation, and identify the supporting and inhibiting factors in managing teacher performance through the PMM that affect the teaching and learning process.

Data were collected from the field, analyzed, and triangulated to strengthen the validity of findings. A summary of the results is presented below:

Table 1. Summary of Research Findings on the Impact of Teacher Performance Management on the Merdeka Mengajar Platform (PMM) on the Teaching and Learning Process at SMA Negeri 5 Bengkulu

No	Research Aspect	Impact on Teaching and Learning Process
1	Teacher Performance Planning on PMM	1. Teachers received clear guidance on competency development from the platform. 2. Teachers gained access to continuous professional development programs designed to enhance teaching competencies. 3. Teachers improved their instructional planning using the Work Outcome Plan. 4. Teachers became more focused on improving teaching practices.
2	Teacher Performance Implementation on PMM	1. Teachers were provided with clear tools and guidance to conduct teaching and learning activities. 2. Teachers focused more on motivating students. 3. Teachers applied more varied teaching methods. 4. Teachers utilized multiple teaching resources.
3	Teacher Performance Evaluation on PMM	1. Evaluation targets became clearer and more achievable. 2. Effective learning performance indicators were achieved. 3. Evaluations served as a starting point for performance improvement. 4. Administrative tasks became easier for teachers.
4	Supporting and Inhibiting Factors	Supporting factors: availability of relevant features that facilitate planning and implementation, strong institutional support, professional training, and teacher commitment. Inhibiting factors: limited time and heavy workload, lack of supervision, unsynchronized features, challenges in managing large classrooms, and low motivation or commitment.

1. Impact of Performance Planning

The first finding indicates that teachers received clear guidance from the PMM in developing competencies. The platform offers continuous professional development programs designed to enhance teaching effectiveness. Competency development refers to efforts made to enhance teachers' knowledge and skills to improve learning through the use of the Work Outcome Plan (Astutiningtyas, Kusumaningsih, & Nurkolis, 2025).

Second, performance planning through the PMM encouraged teachers to focus more on improving teaching practices. Teachers used appropriate indicators based on their school's *Education Report Card* to guide their practice (Musakirawati, 2023:202). Structured planning leads to more productive teacher-student interactions, increasing engagement and helping tailor content to student needs. Performance planning on PMM provides teachers with structured guidance and encourages better teaching practices, ultimately increasing student engagement. It is a critical process for improving instructional quality (Pangestu, 2022:215).

2. Impact of Performance Implementation

The second finding shows that PMM provides clear tools and guidelines to help teachers implement effective teaching. Teaching involves multiple complex roles, such as being a demonstrator, class manager, facilitator, evaluator, and motivator (Mellyani, 2024:149). To fulfill these roles, structured guidance is essential. The second impact is increased student motivation. Teachers who display passion and use innovative methods can foster enthusiasm and reduce student boredom (Sari, 2021:2260). In this context, the teacher acts as a motivator, creating a dynamic and engaging learning environment.

The third impact is professional growth. Implementation of performance is deeply influenced by the methods teachers use. Innovative methods enhance student participation and improve learning outcomes (Hasriadi, 2022:150). Professional development supports teachers in using creative approaches that improve performance and student achievement. With clear tools and guidance provided by the PMM, teachers can optimize their role as motivators and facilitators, creating an inspiring and innovative classroom environment. This professional development ultimately enhances students' learning interest and outcomes (Hafizi, Hanafiah, & Fatkhullah, 2022).

3. Impact of Performance Evaluation

The third finding shows that systematic performance evaluation provides feedback for teachers to improve their instructional practice. With clear performance indicators, teachers can identify their strengths and weaknesses and adapt strategies to improve teaching effectiveness (Efendi, 2024:82). The second impact is the reinforcement of effective teaching practices. Clear evaluation criteria, classroom observations, and constructive feedback help identify and reward successful teaching strategies, encouraging continuous improvement (Arta, 2024:184; Waluyo & Amalia, 2024).

The third impact is administrative efficiency. PMM simplifies previously complex administrative tasks, such as compiling performance targets (SKP) and documentation for professional development (Wijayanto, 2024). Teachers can now focus more on planning and conducting quality instruction with access to integrated digital tools (Amelia et al., 2022; Sasongko, 2022). Performance evaluation through PMM provides systematic feedback that helps teachers improve their instructional methods, enhances student engagement, and simplifies administrative tasks. This contributes to continuous improvement in teaching and learning outcomes.

4. Supporting and Inhibiting Factors

Supporting factors in performance management through PMM that impact teaching include: (a) the availability of relevant platform features that support instructional planning and execution, (b) strong support from the school, which boosts teacher motivation and confidence, (c) professional training and development opportunities to enhance digital literacy and teaching skills, and (d) teachers' self-awareness and commitment to professional growth, which drive improved teaching practices.

Inhibiting factors include: (a) limited time and heavy workloads, which hinder effective PMM use, (b) insufficient supervision, making performance evaluations more difficult, (c) unsynchronized platform features, limiting innovation, (d) challenges in managing large classes, which affect teacher-student interaction quality, and (e) low motivation and commitment from teachers, which negatively affect instructional effectiveness.

CONCLUSION

Based on the research problems and objectives, the conclusions of this study are described as follows:

First, the impact of teacher performance planning on the *Merdeka Mengajar* Platform (PMM) on the teaching and learning process shows that the PMM guides teachers in identifying performance practices that need improvement based on the *Education Report Card* results of SMA Negeri 5 Bengkulu. This enables teachers to select relevant professional development activities, ultimately leading to improved instructional practices.

Second, the implementation of teacher performance through PMM has a direct impact on teachers by providing clear tools and guidelines for carrying out teaching activities, increasing teacher motivation, and supporting professional development. These factors contribute to greater student engagement in the classroom. Teachers who apply techniques learned from PMM are more likely to adopt a growth mindset and involve students more actively in learning. Moreover, by participating in professional development offered by PMM, teachers gain a better understanding of learning approaches, particularly those related to the *Merdeka Curriculum*, which motivates them to apply this knowledge in the classroom.

Third, performance evaluation through PMM provides valuable feedback on teaching practices and reflects effective teaching methods, ultimately contributing to the improvement of the overall quality of the teaching and learning process. Performance evaluation also simplifies administrative tasks, allowing teachers to focus more on delivering quality instruction and supporting continuous improvement in their teaching practices.

Fourth, supporting factors in teacher performance management on the PMM that positively affect the teaching process include: (a) the availability of relevant features that facilitate planning and instruction, (b) strong support from the school that enhances teacher motivation and confidence, (c) professional training and development that equip teachers with the skills to use the platform optimally, and (d) teachers' awareness and commitment to self-improvement, which promotes better teaching practices.

In contrast, inhibiting factors include: (a) limited time and heavy workloads that hinder effective PMM utilization, (b) lack of supervision, making evaluation processes difficult, (c) feature mismatches on the PMM that inhibit innovation in teaching, (d) challenges in managing large classes, reducing the quality of teacher-student interaction, and (e) lack of motivation and personal commitment from teachers, which can diminish the effectiveness of the teaching and learning process.

In general, the findings of this study, titled "*The Impact of Teacher Performance Management on the Merdeka Mengajar Platform (PMM) on the Teaching and Learning Process at SMA Negeri 5 Bengkulu*", indicate that teacher performance management on the PMM has significant impacts on the teaching and learning process. Performance planning helps teachers select areas for improvement based on the Education Report Card and choose relevant competency development activities. Performance implementation provides tools and guidance that enhance instruction and student engagement through improved motivation and professional development. Systematic performance evaluation offers meaningful feedback, recognizes effective practices, and simplifies administrative tasks. Supporting factors include accessible platform features, school support, professional training, and teacher commitment. Inhibiting factors involve time constraints, limited supervision, system limitations, instructional challenges, and lack of motivation, all of which may hinder the optimal implementation of teaching and reduce the quality of student interaction.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following are recommendations for various stakeholders: First, education supervisors should provide direct assistance to teachers in using the PMM, ensuring that all teachers understand how to use the platform and receive constructive feedback. Furthermore, supervisors should propose that institutions adopt a performance evaluation standard based on the use of the PMM to encourage all teachers to use the platform more effectively.

Second, school principals are expected to facilitate teachers in preparing their *Work Outcome Plans (RHK)* that integrate technology into instructional activities. This includes allocating time and resources for such activities. Principals should also promote teacher collaboration by creating forums or discussion groups to share best practices and experiences in using the PMM.

Third, teachers are encouraged to actively participate in training and workshops related to the PMM and to continuously update their knowledge and skills in educational technology. Teachers should also adopt diverse teaching methods and utilize the available PMM features to enhance student interaction during the learning process.

Fourth, future research should be conducted over a longer time span to capture changes in teacher performance management and instructional practices. Future studies should also investigate external factors affecting technology use in education, such as parental support and students' socioeconomic environment. Comparative studies across schools or regions are also recommended to gain a broader understanding of the successes and challenges in implementing the PMM.

By implementing these recommendations, it is expected that the quality of teacher performance management and the teaching and learning process at SMA Negeri 5 Bengkulu will improve, thus making a positive contribution to the broader educational landscape.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The researcher would like to express sincere gratitude to the Principal and fellow teachers of SMA Negeri 5 Bengkulu who willingly served as informants and contributed to the successful completion of this research.

REFERENCES

1. Agraini, T. R. (2024). The effectiveness of using the Merdeka Mengajar Platform application in improving teacher competence at SMKN 1 Singingi Hilir. *Jurnal Teknik Industri Terintegrasi (JUTIN)*, 7(3), 1551–1559.
2. Amelia, U., Widiawati, F. A., Monia, F. A., Hanafi, I., & Mandasari, M. (2022). The effect of teacher performance on online learning in facing the COVID-19 pandemic and the new normal era. In *Proceedings of the 2nd Padang International Conference on Educational Management and Administration 2021* (pp. 197–202). Atlantis Press. https://doi.org/10.2991/978-2-494069-11-4_20
3. An'ars, M. G. (2022). Key Performance Indicator (KPI)-based management information systems in measuring teacher performance. *Jurnal Data Mining dan Sistem Informasi*, 3(1), 8–18.
4. Ardiansyah. (2023). Data collection techniques and research instruments in educational scientific research using qualitative and quantitative approaches. *IHSAN: Jurnal Pendidikan Islam*, 1(2), 1–9.
5. Arta, G. Y. (2024). Assessment in education: Concepts, approaches, principles, types, and functions. *Jurnal Pendidikan, Bahasa dan Budaya*, 3(3), 170–190.

6. Astutiningtyas, D. N. L., Kusumaningsih, W., & Nurkolis, N. (2025). Transforming education: How teacher performance management and appreciative inquiry leadership improve learning quality. *Al Ishlah: Jurnal Pendidikan*, 17(2), 1–xx. <https://doi.org/10.35445/alishlah.v17i2.7069>
7. Efendi, N. (2024). Educational management in improving learning quality. *Academicus: Journal of Teaching and Learning*, 2(2), 68–85.
8. Hafizi, I. W., Hanafiah, & Fatkhullah, F. K. (2022). Management of teacher competency development and training in improving learning quality. *Journal of Education Research and Evaluation*, 6(3), 520–528. <https://doi.org/10.23887/jere.v6i3.52673>
9. Haryono, E. (2023). Qualitative research methodology in Islamic higher education institutions. *An-Nuur: The Journal of Islamic Studies*, 13(2), 1–13.
10. Hasriadi, H. (2022). Innovative learning methods in the era of digitalization. *Jurnal Sinestesia*, 12(1), 136–151.
11. Imelda, C. (2024). Legal foundation for managing teacher and principal performance through the Merdeka Mengajar Platform (PMM) integrated with the National Civil Service Agency's e-Kinerja system. *Multidisciplinary Indonesian Center Journal (MICJO)*, 1(1), 278–283.
12. Kemendikbudristek. (2023). *Substance Guide for Managing Teacher & Principal Performance: Merdeka Mengajar Platform Series*. Jakarta: Ministry of Education, Culture, Research, and Technology.
13. Kompas. (2024, January 30). Teachers overwhelmed by various educational applications. *Kompas*, p. 5.
14. Kumala, D. A. R. (2022). Human resource development strategies. *Jurnal Penelitian dan Pengembangan Sains dan Humaniora*, 6(2), 254–264.
15. Kurnia, A. D. (2023). Utilization of management information systems in the PDUM application to improve final year students' exam performance. *Jurnal Administrasi Pendidikan*, 5(1), 83–94.
16. Media Literasi Nusantara (Melintas). (2024, January 24). Are teachers really anxious about performance management on the PMM application? Let's listen to what a character education expert has to say (pp. 1–3).
17. Media Literasi Nusantara (Melintas). (2024, January 30). Merdeka Curriculum causes concern: Teachers busy with administration and training, students neglected (pp. 1–3).
18. Mellyani, P. C. (2024). Identifying the role of teachers in optimizing mathematics learning management at SMPK 2 Harapan. *Edukasia: Jurnal Pendidikan dan Pembelajaran*, 5(1), 149–154.
19. Munawir, M. (2022). The performance of professional elementary school teachers. *JPG: Jurnal Pendidikan Guru*, 3(1), 8–14.
20. Musakirawati. (2023). Utilization of the Education Report Card Platform. *Jurnal Dinamika Manajemen Pendidikan (JDMP)*, 7(2), 201–208.
21. Nkundabakura, P. (2022). Teacher performance, attitude, and classroom practices dataset collected to evaluate the Rwandan Quality Basic Education project. *Data in Brief*, 45, 108758. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dib.2022.108758>
22. Pangestu, R. N. (2022). Factors affecting employee performance: Planning, quality, and leadership (A literature review of performance management). *Jurnal Ilmu Manajemen Terapan*, 4(2), 215–228.
23. Paudpedia. (2024, January 23). Features of teacher and principal performance management integrated with the National Civil Service Agency's e-Kinerja.
24. Sari, W. N. (2021). The role of teachers in increasing motivation and learning interest of fifth-grade students at SDN Tambahmulyo 1. *Jurnal Inovasi Penelitian*, 1(11), 2255–2262.
25. ScienceDirect. (2024). Professional learning communities and their impact on teacher performance: Empirical evidence from public primary schools in Guiyang. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 148, Article 104715. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2024.104715>
26. Shokhiyatun, S. (2023). Character education management through class-based approaches. *Jurnal Inovasi Pembelajaran di Sekolah*, 4(2), 326–333.
27. Tirtoni, F. (2024). Optimizing the role of teachers in teaching. *Jurnal Pengabdian Kepada Masyarakat*, 4(1).
28. Tommy. (2019). Definitions according to experts. Retrieved from <https://www.kotakpintar.com>

-
29. Waluyo, H. S., & Amalia, N. (2024). The impact of teachers' classroom management skills on learning. *Didaktika Tauhidi: Jurnal Pendidikan Guru Sekolah Dasar*, 11(1), 47–60. <https://doi.org/10.30997/dt.v11i1.12699>
30. Wijayanto, P. D. (2024). Collaboration among teachers in handling school administrative tasks. *Jurnal Ilmiah Pendidikan*, 5(4), 76–77.

Cite this Article: Khairiyah, A., Sasongko, R.N., Kartiwi, A.P. (2025). The Impact of Teacher Performance Management on the "Merdeka Mengajar" Platform on the Teaching and Learning Process. International Journal of Current Science Research and Review, 8(7), pp. 3709-3716. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijcsrr/V8-i7-58>